

ADVERSITY QUOTIENT, LEADERSHIP CAPABILITY AND WORK VALUES: A STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODEL ON SCHOOL CULTURE OF TEACHERS

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Adversity Quotient, Leadership Capability and Work Values: A Structural Equation Model on School Culture of Teachers

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Abstract

This study was conducted to determine the best-fit model on school culture of teachers as estimated by adversity quotient of teachers, leadership capability and work values of teachers among public elementary schools in Region XI, Philippines. The study used quantitative, non-experimental correlational research using Structural Equation Model (SEM). The 400 teachers among public elementary schools were determined using the stratified sampling procedure. Mean, Pearson r, and SEM as statistical tools. Moreover, adapted survey questionnaires were used to contextualize to the local setting. The result showed that the level of adversity quotient of teachers was high while the level of leadership capability, work values of teachers and school culture were very high. Further, when each exogenous variable is correlated to school culture, results showed that the adversity quotient of teachers, leadership capability and work values of teachers were correlated with school culture. Model 3 came out as the best-fit model that predicted the school culture of teachers. Further, results showed that the best fit model was model 3 showing the direct causal relationships of adversity quotient, leadership capability and work values on school culture of teachers. Furthermore, structure modifications revealed that school culture of teachers was defined by its retained indicators: professional collaboration, affiliative collegiality, and self-determination/efficacy. On the other hand, adversity quotient was described by its domains: control and endurance. Leadership capability was determined by its retained indicators: cognitive capability and role specific and generic competence. Finally, work values of teachers was determined by its retained indicators: competence and growth, comfort and security and status and independence. Findings of the study may be a significant baseline for faculty development programs of educational institutions.

Keywords: *educational management, adversity quotient, leadership capability, work values, school culture*

Introduction

Problems on school culture contribute to teacher burnout and underappreciation. Such urgent problems include under staffing, disengaged parents, time-consuming meetings, and balancing administrative duties among teachers. Recently, teachers are also becoming overwhelmed in many aspects wherein they teach with low emotional commitment and poor sense of efficacy (Kim, 2023). Moreover, the low quality of education is an urgent challenge. The intense pressure to raise student performance leads to an exam-oriented school culture. The competitive nature of such system hinders teachers from providing holistic education (Ismail et al., 2022).

Furthermore, school culture has an important role in maintaining commitment that have been agreed so that all activities carried out at school follow the vision, mission, and goals. Inculcating positive values in school culture increases willingness, loyalty and teacher performance (Muhsin et al., 2020). Relatedly, school culture plays an important role in the emergence of what is expected from teachers. It promotes the personal growth and self-learning of teachers wherein it supports the activities at school (Bayar & Karaduman, 2021).

In a previous study, adversity quotient has a significant relationship with work ethics, school culture, and teacher performance. There is a need to improve adversity quotient as it positively affects student performance (Safi'I et al., 2021). Relatedly, another study found out that increasing adversity quotient, school culture, and job satisfaction will also increase teacher commitment. Teachers are expected to have high adversity quotient for school activities to operate smoothly especially during difficult situations (Virgana et al., 2022).

In addition, a related study found out that a productive school culture depends upon school improvement, leadership capability, stakeholder partnership and teacher performance. Leadership capability should be improved so that teachers can mold a positive culture in schools and increase student performance (Jabonillo, 2022). Similarly, a previous study determined that leadership capability promotes school culture which impacts teacher productivity, satisfaction, student achievement, and overall school engagement. There is a need for leaders to understand the factors that lead to improvement to ensure that schools run smoothly (Chickite, 2021).

A similar study highlighted that teachers who successfully meet work values efforts could create an open school culture. Such culture attracts visitors and stakeholders which lead to better school administration (Queroda & Lincod, 2020). There is also a need to create a positive school culture as it provides teachers the work values which are a characteristic of the organization wherein each member of the organization is given guidelines on the enforcement of work discipline. Teachers need to inculcate work values and school culture so that they can integrate themselves as an important part of the school culture system (Lubis & Hanum, 2020).

Furthermore, the researcher had not come across a study that dealt with a structural equation model on school culture of teachers in the local setting. It was in this context that the researcher was interested to determine whether factors such as adversity quotient, leadership capability, and work values significantly influence the school culture of teachers in Region XI as this can raise concern to the intended beneficiaries of this study may also be developed to improve adversity quotient, leadership capability and work values and consequently

augment the school culture of teachers; thus, the need to conduct this study.

The main thrust of this study was to determine the best fit model of school culture of teachers as estimated by adversity quotient of teachers, leadership capability and work values of teachers among public elementary schools in Region XI. Specifically, it aimed to describe the level of adversity quotient of teachers in terms of control, ownership, reach and endurance. It also aimed to ascertain the level of leadership capability in terms of personal capabilities, interpersonal capability, cognitive capability and role-specific and generic competencies. Further, it aimed to determine the level of work values of teachers in terms of competence and growth, comfort and security and status and independence. Likewise, it aimed to determine the level of school culture in terms of professional collaboration, affiliative collegiality and self-determination/efficacy. Moreover, it aimed to determine the significance of the relationship between adversity quotient of teachers and school culture, leadership capability and school culture, and work values of teachers and school culture. Lastly, it aimed to determine the model best fits the school culture of teachers.

In consonance with the above objectives, the null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. It was hypothesized that there is no significant relationship between adversity quotient of teachers and school culture, leadership capability and school culture, and work values of teachers and school culture. Also, it was hypothesized that there is no model that best fits the school culture of teachers.

The study is anchored on the Organizational Culture Theory by Schein (2006) which posits that organizational culture operates at three interconnected levels. At the surface are artifacts and behaviors. Deeper are espoused values, representing the explicit beliefs an organization professes to uphold. The foundational level consists of basic underlying assumptions, the unconscious and implicit beliefs that guide members' behaviors. Schein contends that to understand and influence organizational culture effectively, one must recognize and address all three levels.

This study is supported by the Social Cognitive Theory of Bandura (1986) which proposes that different individuals tend to maintain various levels of adversity. Personal success is the degree to which individuals move forward and upward despite obstacles and other forms of adversity. Such people continue to rise up and break through and as they persevere, they become more skilled and empowered to tackle the next adversity. People who identify similar opportunities and are exposed to similar economic and business obstacles differ in the way they perceive and react to adversity.

This study is also supported by the Upper Echelon Theory of Hambrick and Mason (1984) which highlights that an organization's strategy and level of enterprise performance rely on the background of the top managers in that organization. The education level and working experience influence these managers with specific skills, as portrayed in various leadership capabilities. Such differences in leadership capabilities influence performance. The theory looks into the correlation between leadership capability and enterprise performance.

Previous studies show that teacher adversity quotient impacts pedagogic success which is an indicator of teacher professional competence. It helps teachers improve their abilities and perseverance in facing challenges and achieving satisfaction which in turn, has a positive effect on teacher performance. Adversity quotient affects learning behaviors and learning outcomes making it vital for organizational life (Widodo et al., 2022; Zhao et al., 2021). The teachers' ability to overcome issues in their daily lives are assessed using adversity quotient. A teacher with high adversity quotient is a diligent worker equipped with strong self-control (Saguni et al., 2021).

Additionally, teachers who manifest control perceive that they have a strong degree of control over adverse events and view success and adversity as originating from external sources. Teachers with task and connection focus also have strong degree of control wherein they view success as enduring. Another study found out that teachers with higher education qualifications have higher control over their work and required less supervision compared to those with less educational qualification. Teachers with long experience use better classroom management and teaching methods that encourage student autonomy and control; thus, managing classroom problems and keeping students on task (Mwivanda, 2021; Tansiongco & Ibarra, 2020).

In a previous study, teachers with a high level of reach exert effort to reach their goals, persist longer in the face of adversity, and rise up from setbacks. It is important for teachers to set a limit to the reach of adversity. Adversities happening in school must not reach their personal life, and at the same time, adverse events in their personal lives must not affect their job. Similarly, teachers with high reach see adversity in a different perspective. They do not allow adversity to hinder other parts of their life as well as believe that adversity affects only a particular situation (Mamino, 2021; Yazon, 2019).

Further, teacher leadership capability is highly dependent on the support of the school administration. To take advantage of teachers' expertise and experiences, school leaders must provide professional development opportunities, and assign responsibility for implementing innovative ideas. There is a need to implement teacher leadership training that will result in leadership capability. In another study, the development of leadership capability enables the achievement of educational goals, the improvement of quality of teacher training, and the development of leadership capability skills. Leadership capability is manifested in teamwork and has an interactive nature, determined by situational factors, self-realization and ability to influence the situation (Afanasjeva, 2019; Carswell, 2021).

Teacher personal capabilities motivate students to continue attending a class. In a previous study, effective teachers are innovative,

invite students to interactions, and value diversity. Teachers who have the capability to inspire students to reach their potential through their qualities and personal capabilities are effective teachers. Relatedly, teacher skills play an important role in supporting students to adapt to changes, including new technologies. Teacher skills linked with personal capabilities are important to individual development (Cubero, 2022; Joynes et al., 2019).

In addition, teacher role-specific and generic competencies involve the knowledge, abilities and skills related to processes and relationships in teaching, possessing the ability to create trust and empathy towards colleagues, creating equal participation in work, among others. Such competencies are important factors in ensuring quality and success at work, and in the teaching process. In a related study, it was found out that teacher performance is influenced by the organizational environment, teacher role-specific and generic competencies and teacher engagement. The said study suggests the use of management approaches that adhere to teachers' needs to promote their development and enhance school quality, teacher competencies and innovation (Simonovic, 2021; Yang & Chang, 2023).

Work values are a good indicator of success. Positive work values are what make the foundation for a good employee. A positive attitude gets the work done and motivates others to do the same without dwelling on the challenges that inevitably come up in any job. In a previous study, work values are linked with motivation and job satisfaction wherein there is a relationship between reaching achievement value and being proactive and taking initiative. If teachers perform their responsibilities effectively, they will be able to achieve the desired goals they want for the students (Giray, 2021; Loretto, 2019).

Moreover, in another study, teacher competence is significantly related to teaching quality, which in turn has an impact on student outcomes. Teacher competence is an important aspect that can be used to improve the quality of teaching and student success such as in professional development programs (Fauth et al., 2019). On the other hand, teacher growth involves teachers engaging in professional learning as practitioners of the art of teaching. Teacher growth results in a need for professional learning that is related to the teacher's work with students. Further, the school context influences teacher growth (Muir et al., 2021).

Teacher status includes the importance of teachers' abilities, recognition in the community, wages and financial benefits. Teachers have higher status than others as they are more valued by society for their roles in professional education, and at the same time their reputation and prestige also increase over time (Mutluer & Yuksel, 2019). Meanwhile, another study found out that teacher independence has a significant impact on how well they work. Independence enables for better performance since it gives teachers more freedom and choice on how to organize their tasks and determine how these will be carried out. The majority of teachers prefer having tasks assigned to them with a deadline and the freedom to complete them (Tingo & Mseti, 2022).

In a previous study, school culture and professional development interact with knowledge and belief to determine teaching and learning. The importance of school culture, professional development and teaching and learning beliefs influence student success. Also, school culture has a mediating effect on leadership style and organizational image. This is due to the realization of the leadership style that has an important role in developing an organizational image, through school culture. Leadership creates a positive effect on the members of the organization and contributes to the creation of good school culture (Kalkan et al., 2020; Lai et al., 2022).

Furthermore, another study highlighted that teacher professional collaboration is important in various school projects and teacher development initiatives including measures to promote relationships between teachers. Teacher professional collaboration is linked with well-being and job satisfaction, wherein teachers in highly dense networks have positive attitudes towards inclusion and differentiated instruction. Relatedly, through professional collaboration, teachers are diversifying their teaching strategies, and reflect on their own practice, thus attaining professional growth and providing opportunities for educational change. Teacher professional collaboration promotes professional development as it provides the opportunity for teachers to work together (Kolleck et al., 2021; Richit et al., 2021).

Teacher self-determination or efficacy is linked with positive outcomes such as increased adaptability, task engagement, self-confidence and well-being. It facilitates the teacher's ongoing growth and engagement in their surroundings. Teacher self-determination has a significant impact on all students. Teaching strategies such as self-regulation, motivation and self-advocacy can be effective in promoting the improvement of self-determination in teachers, and academic skills in students (Baird, 2020; Brenner, 2022).

Additionally, leadership stimulates teachers to have information with regards to helping the school successfully balance its responsibilities. There is a need to lead the school with innovation, diversity, and favorable attitudes toward the organization (Blas & Guhao, 2023). In terms of work values, teachers could enhance the climate of helpfulness among members of the school community through teamwork in realizing the school's vision and mission. Teachers should internalize and practice the policies, standards and guidelines of their respective departments (Guhao, 2023). Lastly, school culture has a significant correlation with professional learning communities. School culture was measured by its domains affiliative collegiality and professional collaboration wherein such findings could serve as a reference for faculty development programs of schools (Guhao & Sioting, 2023).

On a global perspective, studies on school culture aid in obtaining insights into how school culture impacts the success of schooling. School culture is an important factor that contributes to the effective functioning of a school (Ismail et al., 2022). Moreover, studies on school culture may facilitate the achievement of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal No. 4 on ensuring inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all (United Nations, 2024). In terms of society, studies on school culture could help promote a positive school culture formed by the school heads, teachers, and students. The close relations

between the school heads, teachers, and students supports the realization of the common goals of the school (Bayar & Karaduman, 2021).

The findings of this study may be beneficial to the Department of Education, school heads, teachers and even future researchers. The result of the study may give information to the Department of Education officials regarding the adversity quotient, leadership capability, work values and school culture which may serve as the basis for the formulation of plans and programs that may augment these among schools leading to attaining school effectiveness especially with the student academic success. Moreover, the result of the study may be beneficial to the school heads since they find effective mechanisms to improve their ability to adjust to adversities in management and their capacity to lead teachers in effectively delivering better quality education for the learners. Consequently, findings of this study may also help the teachers in such a way that they may be aware of their adversity quotient and work values. Likewise, this study would serve as springboard of the future researcher for further studies about the related variables and related studies.

Methodology

Research Design

Phenomenological research has an inductive approach to identifying the forms of expression of experiences. It includes examining a case from a subjective point of view (Akturan & Esen, 2013).

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the 400 teachers taken from the 10 school divisions in Region XI, Philippines for the school year 2022-2023. The researcher utilized the maximum sample in the Slovin's formula with 400 at 0.05 level of significance (Yamane, 1967). Stratified random method was used in determining the respondents of the study. Stratified random sampling is a method of sampling that involves the division of a population into smaller sub-groups known as strata which are formed based on members' shared attributes or characteristics such as income or educational attainment (Hayes, 2024).

Moreover, the researchers considered the inclusion, exclusion and withdrawal criteria in the selection of the respondents of the study. In particular, included as respondents were the regular teachers among public elementary schools in 10 divisions of Region XI whose plantilla numbers are in the Department of Education. These teachers were all public elementary school teachers who were willing to submit themselves as part of the study and were permitted by their school heads to participate in the survey. Those teachers who voluntarily agreed with the informed consent were included in the survey, hence, teachers who clearly confessed their denial were excluded from the study. Also, this study excluded those teachers coming from the private schools or those teachers who hold managerial or supervisory positions. Further, the researcher considered teachers who decided to withdraw or back out during the actual administration of the survey questionnaires if they felt uncomfortable about the study since they were given the free-will to participate without any form of consequence or penalty.

Instruments

The modified survey questionnaire used in this study was made up of four parts which are anchored from a downloaded questionnaire, ie, adversity quotient, leadership capability, work values and school culture. These questionnaires were modified and subjected for validation by experts. The first draft of the research instrument was submitted to the research adviser for comments, suggestions, and recommendations to improve its presentation with the corrections to be included and integrated. The final copies were submitted to a panel of experts for refinement. The final revision was made by incorporating the corrections, comments and suggestions given by the expert validators before the gathering of data. The consolidated results from the experts obtained an average weighted mean of 4.50 which has a verbal description of excellent.

Further, before the administration of the research instrument, a pilot testing was done to selected teachers who were not the respondents of the study. The survey questionnaire for the pilot test was subjected to reliability testing using Internal Consistency Method. This was the most appropriate method to use since the test contains dichotomously scored items which the examinee either passes or fails in an item. The computed reliability of the instrument was > 0.70 for the questionnaire on adversity quotient of teachers, > 0.70 for leadership capability questionnaire, > 0.70 for questionnaire on work values of teachers, and > 0.70 for school culture questionnaire using Cronbach Alpha.

The questionnaire for adversity quotient was adapted from Stoltz (2013) which has the following indicators control, ownership, reach, and endurance. The questionnaire for leadership capability was adapted from Coates et al. (2010) with the following indicators: personal capability, interpersonal capability, cognitive capability, and role-specific and generic competencies. Also, the questionnaire for work values was adapted from Leuty (2010). It has the following indicators: competence and growth, comfort and security, and status and independence. Lastly, the questionnaire for the school culture was adapted from Wagner (2006). The questionnaire for the school culture has the following indicators: professional collaboration, affiliative collegiality, and self-determination/efficacy.

In evaluating the exogenous variables (adversity quotient, leadership capability, work values) and the endogenous variable school culture, the five orderable gradations with their respective range of means and descriptions was used as follows: 4.20 – 5.00 or very high means that the items related to adversity quotient, leadership capability, work values and school culture are always manifested;

3.40 – 4.19 or high means that the items related to adversity quotient, leadership capability, work values and school culture are often manifested; 2.60 – 3.39 or moderate means that the items related to adversity quotient, leadership capability, work values and school culture are sometimes manifested; 1.80 – 2.59 or low means that the items related to adversity quotient, leadership capability, work values and school culture are seldom manifested; and 1.00 – 1.79 or very low means that the items related to adversity quotient, leadership capability, work values and school culture are not manifested at all.

Design and Procedure

The study utilized the quantitative, non-experimental design of research using correlational technique. Correlational technique is a non-experimental design, where the researcher studies the correlation between variables in a normal setting without manipulation or control. In correlational studies, the researchers examine the strength of relationships among variables by looking into how change in one variable is linked with change in the other variable. Generally, correlational method has independent and dependent variables, but the effect of independent variable is seen on dependent variable without manipulating the independent variable (Creswell, 2009).

Likewise, this study used Structural Equation Modeling. According to Li and Lomax (2017), this method combines factor analysis with path analysis to test theoretical relations among latent variables. Here models can range from simple to complex in nature in that any number of variables of any type can be involved (i.e., observed, latent, independent, and/or dependent variables). The incorporation of factor analysis in structural equation modeling allows the researcher to use multiple measures of each latent variable instead of a single measure, thereby enabling better measurement conditions (i.e., reliability and validity) than with a single measure.

Structural equation modeling (SEM) is a powerful, multivariate technique found increasingly in scientific investigations to test and evaluate multivariate causal relationships. Further, SEM includes the statistical method of path analysis. Path analysis, on the other hand, had its beginning in biometrics and aimed to find the causal relationship among variables by creating a path diagram (Wright, 1934). The path analysis in earlier econometrics was presented with simultaneous equations (Haavelmo, 1943). This method was used to measure the relationship between and among adversity quotient of teachers, leadership capability, work values of teachers and school culture among public elementary schools in Region XI, Philippines.

A systematic procedure was followed in the collection of data. The researcher asked permission from the Regional Director of DepEd-Region XI, then to the different Schools Division Superintendent. Upon their approval, the researcher then asked permission to the District Supervisors of each chosen District, and to the School Heads concerned, to allow the researcher to conduct the study to the 400 teachers. Upon the approval, the researcher personally distributed and administered the research instruments to ensure 100 percent retrieval of the questionnaires. During the administration of the survey questionnaire, the researcher made sure that the classes were not interrupted and that possible questions and clarifications from the respondents were personally addressed by the researcher. After all the questionnaires were retrieved, the data were collated, tabulated, interpreted and analyzed based from the research objectives of the study.

The following statistical tools were used in interpreting the data collated. Mean was used to describe the level of adversity quotient of teachers, leadership capability, work values of teachers and school culture in answer to sub-problems 1 to 4. Pearson *r* was used to determine the significance of the relationship between the school culture and the exogenous variables (adversity quotient of teachers, leadership capability, and work values of teachers) in answer to sub-problem 5. Lastly, Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) was used to test the hypothesized models and determine the best fit model for the school culture of teachers among public elementary schools.

In the conduct of this study and before the data were gathered, ethical issues and considerations were considered. The researcher had undergone evaluation conducted by the members of ethics review committee. After several review process, this study was marked as passed and approved by the UM Ethics Review Committee (UMERC). The participation of the respondents was completely voluntary and anonymous to protect their privacy. All public elementary school teachers in Region XI who were involved in the study were given the free-will to participate without any form of consequence or penalty. As a researcher, all data gathered were kept confidential and that such information was utilized only for the purpose of the research. No names were required from the respondents so that their identities become anonymous in adherence to the Data Privacy Act of 2012 which protects the respondents from unauthorized processing of their private or identifiable information or guarantee them that their response cannot be traced back to its real sources to protect their identity.

Informed consent was secured from all the respondents involved in the study. The respondent signed the ICF to prove his/her willingness to participate. It was in a form asking for their voluntary consent in giving their ideas of the said study. The participants were carefully selected based on the criteria provided in the research. The criteria in the selection of respondents included all those public elementary teachers in Region XI and whose plantilla numbers are in the Department of Education. These teachers were all public elementary school teachers who were willing to submit themselves as part of the study and were permitted by their school heads to participate in the survey as they were the ones who are in the position to provide useful information upon testing the hypothesis of the study. No individual answered the questionnaire if he/she did not qualify in the criteria. The study did not involve high risk situations that the respondent experienced in the area of physical, psychological, or socio-economic concerns. It protected and secured the rights of the respondents who were public elementary school teachers and this is conducted in accordance to due process.

All public elementary teachers were the primary beneficiaries of the study and they will be able to gain understanding of the dynamic

of the adversity quotient, leadership capability, work values and school culture in the workplace. The results of this study can help the teachers in their profession since the findings of this study will give them new information about adversity quotient, leadership capability, work values and school culture. In addition, this study will be used as a practical reference for future research in the field of education. Further, in the conduct of this research, the respondents received tangible benefits such as a simple token from the researcher.

The study used the Grammarly or Turnitin software and/ or Plagiarism Detector to ensure that there was no plagiarism to happen in the whole duration of the study. The study underwent the standard procedure of research established by the Professional Schools of the University of Mindanao and all the information presented was carefully written and cited. All sources used in this study came from reliable journals and other scholarly works. There was no trace or indication of deliberate distortion of what was done. The study had no conflict of interest since the researcher had no relationship to the respondents of the study, but it was a requirement for the completion of the master degree in education at the University of Mindanao Professional Schools.

In this study, there was no deceit as everything that was written and reflected was true and underwent validation and thorough checking from different experts in the field of research. The researcher secured proper permission from the targeted agencies where the respondents were teaching/working. There was an online mode of data gathering with the observance of the health and safety protocols as mandated by the government. The researcher sent letters to the Regional Director, Region XI Department of Education, to the Schools Division Superintendent and to the concerned school heads asking for permission to conduct the study. No person was authorized to publish nor present this paper except the researcher or the adviser without the consent of the researcher. For purposes of publication of this study, the adviser becomes the co-authors of the study.

Results and Discussion

Level of Adversity Quotient of Teachers

The data on the adversity quotient of teachers in public elementary schools is shown in Table 1. With a standard deviation of 0.63, the overall mean for the adversity quotient of teachers is 4.08, which is high. This means that adversity quotient is often observed. From this result, among the four indicators of adversity quotient of teachers, control attained the highest mean score of 4.21 or very high with a standard deviation of 0.62 while reach, the lowest, albeit, high gained a standard deviation of 0.83 with a mean score of 3.95. This implies that teacher adversity quotient impacts academic success.

Table 1. *Level of Adversity Quotient of Teachers*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
control	0.62	4.21	Very High
ownership	0.71	4.14	High
reach	0.83	3.95	High
endurance	0.83	4.03	High
Overall	0.63	4.08	High

The results of the study wherein adversity quotient is often observed, is aligned with various authors (Saguni et al., 2021; Widodo et al., 2022; Zhao et al., 2021) wherein adversity quotient affects learning behaviors and learning outcomes, making it vital for organizational life. The teachers' ability to overcome issues in their daily lives are assessed using adversity quotient. A teacher with high adversity quotient is a diligent worker equipped with strong self-control.

Moreover, the indicator control has a very high level. This is congruent with various authors (Mwivanda, 2021; Tansiongco & Ibarra, 2020) who stated that teachers who manifest control perceive that they have strong degree on control over adverse events and view success and adversity as originating from external sources. Teachers with higher education qualifications have higher control over their work and required less supervision compared to those with less educational qualification. Teachers with long experience use better classroom management and teaching methods that encourage student autonomy and control; thus, managing classroom problems and keeping students on task.

Further, the indicator reach has a high level. This is consistent with various authors (Mamino, 2021; Yazon, 2019) who mentioned that teachers with a high level of reach exert effort to reach their goals, persist longer in the face of adversity, and rise up from setbacks. It is important for teachers to set a limit to the reach of adversity. Such teachers with high reach also see adversity from a different perspective. They do not allow adversity to hinder other parts of their life as well as believe that adversity affects only a particular situation.

Level of Leadership Capability

Shown in Table 2 is the data on the level of leadership capability. Computations yielded a standard deviation of 0.60 and an overall mean of 4.45 or very high, and this indicates that the level of leadership capability is always observed. Data reveals that the domain of leadership capability that yielded the highest mean score is the personal capabilities domain with a standard deviation of 0.63 and a mean rating of 4.50 or very high. On the other hand, the lowest indicator, albeit very high is the role-specific and generic competencies which got a standard deviation of 0.64 and a mean score of 4.41. This implies that the school administration highly supports the

teachers' leadership capabilities.

The results of the study on the very high level of leadership capability is coherent with various authors (Afanasjeva, 2019; Carswell, 2021) stating that the development of leadership capability enables the achievement of educational goals, the improvement of quality of teacher training, and the development of leadership capability skills. Leadership capability is manifested in teamwork and has an interactive nature, determined by situational factors, self-realization, and ability to influence the situation.

Table 2. *Level of Leadership Capability*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
Personal Capabilities	0.63	4.50	Very High
Interpersonal Capability	0.65	4.45	Very High
Cognitive Capability	0.67	4.42	Very High
Role-Specific and Generic Competencies	0.64	4.41	Very High
Overall	0.60	4.45	Very High

Also, the indicator personal capabilities has a very high level. The result is congruent with various authors (Cubero, 2022; Joynes et al., 2019) wherein teacher personal capabilities motivate students to continue attending a class. Teachers who have the capability to inspire students to reach their potential through their qualities and personal capabilities are effective teachers. Teacher skills play an important role in supporting students to adapt to changes, including new technologies. Teacher skills linked with personal capabilities are important to individual development.

Furthermore, the indicator role-specific and generic competencies has a very high level. The result is aligned with various authors (Simonovic, 2021; Yang & Chang, 2023) who mentioned that teacher role-specific and generic competencies are important factors in ensuring quality and success at work and in the teaching process. Teacher performance is influenced by the organizational environment, teacher role-specific and generic competencies, and teacher engagement. There is a need to use management approaches that adhere to teachers' needs to promote their development and enhance school quality, teacher competencies, and innovation.

Level of Work Values of Teachers

Shown in Table 3 are the data on the level of work values of teachers. Computations yielded a standard deviation of 0.55 and an overall mean of 4.44, and this indicates that the level of work values of teachers is always manifested. Data reveals that the domain of work values that yielded the highest mean score is competence and growth with a standard deviation of 0.60 and a mean rating of 4.46 or very high. On the other hand, the lowest indicator, albeit very high is the status and independence which got a standard deviation of 0.61 and a mean score of 4.39. This implies that work values positively influence teacher success.

The results of the study on the very high level of work values is consistent with various authors (Giray, 2021; Loretto, 2019) stating that work values are linked with motivation and job satisfaction wherein there is a relationship between reaching achievement value and being proactive and taking initiative. Positive work values are what make the foundation for a good employee. A positive attitude gets the work done and motivates others to do the same without dwelling on the challenges that inevitably come up in any job.

Table 3. *Level of Work Values of Teachers*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
competence and growth	0.60	4.46	Very High
comfort and security	0.60	4.45	Very High
status and independence	0.61	4.39	Very High
Overall	0.55	4.44	Very High

In addition, the indicator competence and growth has a very high level. The result is coherent with various authors (Fauth et al., 2019; Muir et al., 2021) wherein teacher competence is significantly related to teaching quality, which in turn has an impact on student outcomes. Also, teacher growth results in a need for professional learning that is related to the teacher's work with students. Further, the school context influences teacher growth.

Moreover, the indicator status and independence has a very high level. The result is congruent with various authors (Mutluer & Yuksel; Tingo & Mseti, 2022) who mentioned that teachers have higher status than others as they are more valued by society for their roles in professional education, and at the same time their reputation and prestige also increase over time. Further, teacher independence has a significant impact on how well they work. Independence enables for better performance since it gives teachers more freedom and choice on how to organize their tasks and determine how they will be carried out.

Level of School Culture

Shown in Table 4 are the data on the level of school culture. Computations yielded a standard deviation of 0.58 and an overall mean of 4.44 or very high, and this indicates that the school culture is always evident. From this result, the indicator of school culture that yielded the highest mean is professional collaboration with a standard deviation of 0.58 and a mean score of 4.51 or very high, while the lowest indicator, albeit very high is the self-determination/efficacy which gained a standard deviation of 0.65 and a mean score of

4.39. This implies that school culture influences student success.

Table 4. *Level of School Culture*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
Professional collaboration	0.58	4.51	Very High
affiliative collegiality	0.68	4.44	Very High
Self-determination/efficacy	0.65	4.39	Very High
Overall	0.58	4.44	Very High

The results of the study on the very high level of school culture is aligned with various authors (Kalkan et al., 2020; Lai et al., 2022) wherein school culture and professional development interact with knowledge and belief to determine teaching and learning. Leadership style has an important role in developing an organizational image, through school culture. Leadership creates a positive effect on the members of the organization and contributes to the creation of good school culture.

Additionally, the indicator professional collaboration has a very high level. The result is consistent with various authors (Kolleck et al., 2021; Richit et al., 2021) who state that teacher professional collaboration is linked with well-being and job satisfaction wherein teachers in highly dense networks have positive attitudes towards inclusion and differentiated instruction. Through professional collaboration, teachers are diversifying their teaching strategies, and reflect on their own practice; thus, attaining professional growth and providing opportunities for educational change.

Also, the indicator self-determination/efficacy has a very high level. The result is congruent with various authors (Baird, 2020; Brenner, 2022) stating that teacher self-determination or efficacy is linked with positive outcomes such as increased adaptability, task engagement, self-confidence and well-being. Teacher self-determination has a significant impact on all students. Teaching strategies such as self-regulation, motivation and self-advocacy can be effective in promoting the improvement of self-determination in teachers, and academic skills in students.

Correlation between Adversity Quotient of Teachers and School Culture

One important purpose of this study was to determine whether adversity quotient of teachers has a correlation with school culture. The results of the computations are shown in Table 5. As shown in the table, the overall r-value on the correlation between the level of adversity quotient of teachers and the level of school culture is 0.486 with p-value of <0.000, which means that adversity quotient of teachers is significantly associated with the school culture. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Furthermore, when the domains of adversity quotient of teachers were correlated to overall school culture of teachers, results of the computation yielded the r- values ranging from 0.329 to 0.490 with a p-value of <0.000, respectively which can be all interpreted as significant. These factors are significantly related to the domains of school culture with r-values ranging from 0.406 to 0.467 with p-value of <0.000 which signify significant relationships. This implies that school culture is affected by adversity quotient.

Table 5. *Correlation between Adversity Quotient and School Culture*

<i>Adversity Quotient</i>	<i>School Culture</i>			
	<i>professional collaboration</i>	<i>affiliative collegiality</i>	<i>self-determination/ efficacy</i>	<i>Overall</i>
Control	.415* (0.000)	.423* (0.000)	.427* (0.000)	.466* (0.000)
Ownership	.416* (0.000)	.427* (0.000)	.485* (0.000)	.490* (0.000)
Reach	.250* (0.000)	.309* (0.000)	.328* (0.000)	.329* (0.000)
Endurance	.319* (0.000)	.355* (0.000)	.357* (0.000)	.381* (0.000)
Overall	.406* (0.000)	.442* (0.000)	.467* (0.000)	.486* (0.000)

*Significant at 0.05 significance level.

There is a significant relationship between adversity quotient and school culture. The findings of the study are consistent with various authors (Safi'I et al., 2021; Virgana et al., 2022) wherein adversity quotient has a significant relationship with work ethics, school culture and teacher performance. Increasing adversity quotient, school culture and job satisfaction will also increase teacher commitment. Teachers are expected to have high adversity quotient for school activities to operate smoothly especially during difficult situations.

Correlation between Leadership Capability and School Culture

Another purpose of this study was to determine whether leadership capability has a correlation with school culture. The results of the computations are shown in Table 6. The overall r-value on the correlation between the level of leadership capability and the level of school culture was 0.725 with p-value of <0.000, which means that the leadership capability is significantly associated with the school

culture. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 6. *Correlation between Leadership Capability and School Culture*

Leadership Capability	School Culture			Overall
	Professional Collaboration	Affiliative Collegiality	Self-Determination/Efficacy	
Personal Capabilities	.623* (0.000)	.556* (0.000)	.542* (0.000)	.632* (0.000)
Interpersonal Capability	.622* (0.000)	.583* (0.000)	.545* (0.000)	.644* (0.000)
Cognitive Capability	.679* (0.000)	.655* (0.000)	.608* (0.000)	.715* (0.000)
Role-Specific and Generic Competencies	.659* (0.000)	.634* (0.000)	.596* (0.000)	.695* (0.000)
Overall	.697* (0.000)	.655* (0.000)	.618* (0.000)	.725* (0.000)

*Significant at 0.05 significance level.

Moreover, when the domains of leadership capability of teachers were correlated to overall school culture of teachers, results of the computation yielded the r-values ranging from 0.632 to 0.715 with p-values of <0.000 respectively, which can be all interpreted as significant. These factors are significantly related to the domains of school culture with r-values ranging from 0.618 to 0.697 with p-value of <0.000 which signify significant relationships. This also implies that leadership capability effectively promotes school culture.

There is also a significant relationship between leadership capability and school culture. The findings of the study are congruent with various authors (Chickite, 2021; Jabonillo, 2022) stating that a productive school culture depends upon school improvement, leadership capability, stakeholder partnership and teacher performance. Leadership capability should be improved so that teachers can mold a positive culture in schools and increase student performance. Leadership capability promotes school culture which impacts teacher productivity, satisfaction, student achievement, and overall school engagement.

Correlation between Work Values of Teachers and School Culture

This present study also aimed to determine whether work values of teachers has a correlation with school culture. The results of the computations are shown in Table 7. The overall r-value on the correlation between the level of work values of teachers and the level of the school culture was 0.725 with p-value of <0.000, which means that the work values of teachers is significantly associated with the school culture. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 7. *Correlation between Work Values and School Culture*

Work Values	School Culture			Overall
	Professional Collaboration	Affiliative Collegiality	Self-Determination/Efficacy	
Competence and Growth	.703* (0.000)	.689* (0.000)	.651* (0.000)	.753* (0.000)
Comfort and Security	.704* (0.000)	.616* (0.000)	.641* (0.000)	.720* (0.000)
Status and Independence	.736* (0.000)	.644* (0.000)	.668* (0.000)	.752* (0.000)
Overall	.778* (0.000)	.707* (0.000)	.711* (0.000)	.807* (0.000)

*Significant at 0.05 significance level.

In addition, when the domains of work values of teachers such were correlated to school culture of teachers, results of the computation yielded the r-values of 0.720 to 0.753 with p-value of <0.000, respectively, which can be all interpreted as significant. These factors are significantly related to the domains of school culture with r-values ranging from 0.707 to 0.778 with p-values of <0.000 which signify significant relationships. This also implies that school culture is significantly impacted by the work values of teachers.

There is also a significant relationship between work values and school culture. The findings of the study are aligned with various authors (Lubis & Hanum, 2020; Queroda & Lincod, 2020) who mentioned that teachers who successfully meet work values efforts could create an open school culture. Teachers need to inculcate work values and school culture so that they can integrate themselves as an important part of the school culture system.

Best Fit Model on School Culture

The original proposed model some modification to fit the data. There were three generated models presented in the study. In identifying the best fit model, all indices included must consistently fall within the acceptable ranges. Chi-square/ degrees of freedom value should be less than 2 but greater than 0 with its corresponding p-value greater than 0.05. Root mean square error approximation value must be

less than 0.05 and its corresponding P-close value must be greater than 0.05. The other indices such as the normed fit index, Tucker-Lewis index, comparative fit index and the goodness of fit index must all be greater than 0.95.

Generated Model 1. Shown in Figure 1 is Hypothesized Model 1 in standardized solution. It is a tested model depicting the interrelationships between the latent exogenous variable school culture. In assessing the absolute fit of Generated Model 1, it can be extracted from Table 8 that the Chi-square/ Degrees of freedom (CMINDF) of 3.028 provided a poor fit, Goodness of Fit Index (GFI) of 0.926 did not offer a good support for the model, and Root Means Square of Error Approximation (RMSEA) of 0.071 did not satisfy the criterion to be reasonably fit. When assessing the comparative fit measures, the results revealed that Comparative Fit Index (CFI) was 0.893. Normed Fit Index (NFI) was 0.869 and Tucker Lewis Index (TLI) was 0.873; therefore it did not fall within the acceptable criteria and did not provide support to the model. Moreover, the P-value (0.000) was not higher than 0.05 and P-Close (0.001) was not higher than 0.05. Overall, Structural Model 1 was a very poorly fit model as it failed to pass each of the criteria.

Figure 1. Structural Model 1 in Standardized Solution

Table 8. Goodness of Fit Measures of Structural Equation Model 1

Index	Criterion	Model Fit Value
P-Close	> 0.05	.001
CMIN/DF	0 < value < 2	3.028
P-value	> 0.05	.000
GFI	> 0.95	.926
CFI	> 0.95	.970
NFI	> 0.95	.956
TLI	> 0.95	.962
RMSEA	< 0.05	.071

CMIN/DF - Chi-Square/Degrees of Freedom; NFI - Normed Fit Index; TLI - Tucker-Lewis Index; CFI - Comparative Fit Index; GFI - Goodness of Fit Index; RMSEA - Root Means Square of Error Approximation; Pclose - P of Close Fit; P-value - Probability Level

Generated Model 2. A model modification approach (Kline, 2005) was warranted by testing the hypothesized model and removing indicators or variables to improve the fit of the data. To apply this approach, reflected in Figure 2 is Hypothesized Model 2 in standardized solution. It is a tested model showing the interrelationships between the exogenous variables adversity quotient, leadership capability, and work values and its causal relationship on school culture. It can also be noticed that the model was slightly modified by taking out two indicators (ownership and reach) from the endogenous variable adversity quotient leaving control and endurance; also, two indicators (personal capability and interpersonal capability) taken out from the endogenous variable leadership capability leaving cognitive capability, and role-specific and generic competence.

In assessing the absolute fit of Generated Model 2, it can be extracted from Table 9 that Chi-square/ Degrees of freedom (CMINDF) of 2.056 provided a poor fit, Goodness of Fit Index (GFI) of 0.971 did not offer a good support for the model, and Root Means Square of Error Approximation (RMSEA) of 0.051 did not satisfy the criterion to be reasonably fit. When assessing the comparative fit measures, the results revealed that Comparative Fit Index (CFI) was 0.990. Normed Fit Index (NFI) was 0.981 and Tucker Lewis Index (TLI) was 0.985; implying that it did not fall within the acceptable criteria and did not provide support to the model. Moreover, the P-value (0.001) was not higher than 0.05 and P-Close (0.423) was not higher than 0.05.

Figure 2. Structural Equation Model 2 in Standardized Solution

Table 9. Goodness of Fit Measures of Structural Equation Model 2

Index	Criterion	Model Fit Value
P-Close	> 0.05	.423
CMIN/DF	0 < value < 2	2.056
P-value	> 0.05	.001
GFI	> 0.95	.971
CFI	> 0.95	.990
NFI	> 0.95	.981
TLI	> 0.95	.985
RMSEA	< 0.05	.051

CMIN/DF - Chi-Square/Degrees of Freedom; NFI - Normed Fit Index; TLI - Tucker-Lewis Index; CFI - Comparative Fit Index; GFI - Goodness of Fit Index; RMSEA - Root Means Square of Error Approximation; Pclose - P of Close Fit; P-value - Probability Level

Generated Model 3. Exhibited in Figure 3 is Hypothesized Model 3 in standardized solution in consonance with Klines (2005) model modification approach. It is a tested model showing direct causal link of the variables towards school culture and its interrelationships among variables. This model was a modified version of the previous two models.

Figure 3. *Structural Equation Model 3 in Standardized Solution*Table 10. *Goodness of Fit Measures of Structural Equation Model 3*

<i>Index</i>	<i>Criterion</i>	<i>Model Fit Value</i>
P-Close	> 0.05	.846
CMIN/DF	0 < value < 2	1.458
P-value	> 0.05	.080
GFI	> 0.95	.983
CFI	> 0.95	.996
NFI	> 0.95	.989
TLI	> 0.95	.994
RMSEA	< 0.05	.034

CMIN/DF - Chi-Square/Degrees of Freedom; *NFI* - Normed Fit Index; *TLI* - Tucker-Lewis Index; *CFI* - Comparative Fit Index; *GFI* - Goodness of Fit Index; *RMSEA* - Root Means Square of Error Approximation; *Pclose* - P of Close Fit; *P-value* - Probability Level

The Latent exogenous variable adversity quotient has two indicators remaining: control and endurance; also, latent exogenous variable leadership capability has two indicators remaining: cognitive capability, and role-specific and generic competence; further, latent exogenous variable work values has two indicators remaining: competence and growth, and comfort and security.

Moreover, presented in Table 10 is the goodness of fit measures of Structural Model 3. It can be derived from the table that Model 3 came out as the best fit model satisfying the criteria for the standard-fit because of the causal model data fitting using Pearson r , which should be significant. Other criteria to be considered to have a good model fit are as follows: a value of 0.95 or greater for CFI, which is the comparative fit index (Byrne, 2001), RMSEA value of less than 0.05, which is the root means square of error approximation (Meyers, Gamst & Guarino, 2006), NFI or normed fit index value of more than 0.95 (Hu & Bentler, 1999). Model 3 has satisfied all these criteria, showing that the NFI is 0.989 more than 0.95, the CFI is 0.996 greater than 0.95, and TLI is 0.994 greater than 0.95. Also, the indicators of CMIN/DF of 1.458 with its conforming p-value of 0.080, while the RMSEA is 0.034 less than 0.05 with P-close = 0.846. Thus, Structural Model 3 is the best fit in totality.

The model clearly illustrates the importance of adversity quotient, leadership capability, and work values towards school culture. Adversity quotient, leadership capability and work values contribute to the improvement of the school culture of teachers. Thus, the findings suggest that the school culture of teachers is rooted on the strong evidence of adversity quotient: control and endurance; leadership capability: cognitive capability, and role-specific and generic competence; and work values: competence and growth, and comfort and security.

In Hypothesized Model 3 is shown the interrelationship between the exogenous variables: adversity quotient, leadership capability, and work values and its causal relationship on the endogenous variable school culture. Results suggest that the exogenous variables adversity quotient represented by the measured indicators: control and endurance; leadership capability represented by the measured indicators: cognitive capability, and role-specific and generic competence; and work values represented by the measured indicators - competence and growth, and comfort and security have a significant contribution to the endogenous variable school culture.

The result is aligned with the model modification approach by Kline (2005) which clearly illustrated the importance of adversity quotient, leadership capability, and work values towards school culture. School culture is considered to be positively predicted by effective adversity quotient, while control and endurance are the remaining significant indicators of adversity quotient. Adversity quotient has a significant relationship with work ethics, school culture and teacher performance. Increasing adversity quotient, school culture and job satisfaction will also increase teacher commitment (Safi'I et al., 2021; Virgana et al., 2022).

Moreover, leadership capability can impact school culture. Cognitive capability, and role-specific and generic competence are the remaining significant indicators of leadership capability. A productive school culture depends upon school improvement, leadership capability, and teacher performance. Leadership capability promotes school culture which impacts teacher productivity, satisfaction, student achievement, and overall school engagement (Chickite, 2021; Jabonillo, 2022).

Further, work values positively predict school culture. Competence and growth, and comfort and security are the remaining significant indicators of school culture. Teachers who successfully meet work values efforts could create an open school culture. There is a need to create a positive school culture as it provides teachers the work values which are a characteristic of the organization wherein each member of the organization is given guidelines on the enforcement of work discipline (Lubis & Hanum, 2020; Queroda & Lincod, 2020).

In addition, the results of the endogenous variable (school culture) with its significant indicators (professional collaboration, affiliative collegiality, and self-determination/efficacy) have its results summed up and supported by various authors (Guhao & Sioting, 2023) who stated that school culture has a significant correlation with professional learning communities. School culture was measured by its domains affiliative collegiality and professional collaboration wherein such findings could serve as a reference for faculty development programs of schools.

Lastly, the results of the study are congruent with the statements by Schein (2006) on the Organizational Culture Theory, which posits that organizational culture operates at three interconnected levels. At the surface are artifacts and behaviors. Deeper are espoused values, representing the explicit beliefs an organization professes to uphold. The foundational level consists of basic underlying assumptions, the unconscious and implicit beliefs that guide members' behaviors. To understand and influence organizational culture effectively, one must recognize and address all three levels.

Conclusions

Based from the findings of the study, the researcher came up with the following conclusions. The mean level of adversity quotient is high. In addition, the mean levels of leadership capability, work values, and school culture are very high. There are also significant relationships between adversity quotient and school culture, leadership capability and school culture, and work values and school culture. Results also revealed that among the three structural models, Model 3 is the model which best fits school culture of teachers.

All of the exogenous variables - adversity quotient represented by the measured indicators: control and endurance; leadership capability represented by the measured indicators cognitive capability, and role-specific and generic competence; and work values represented by the measured indicators competence and growth, and comfort and security have significant contribution to the endogenous variable school culture. This study is supported by the anchor theory, the Organizational Culture Theory by Schein (2006) which posits that organizational culture operates at three interconnected levels. In order to understand and influence organizational culture effectively, one must recognize and address all three levels.

The researcher came up with recommendations based on the results of the study. It was revealed that the following indicators got the lowest means: reach for adversity quotient of teachers; role-specific and generic competencies for leadership capability; status and independence for work values of teachers, and self-determination/efficacy for school culture. To address the issue on the level of reach for adversity quotient of teachers, the Department of Education (DepEd) and school heads may prioritize the implementation of resilience-building workshops and training programs to enhance teachers' capacity to handle criticism, setbacks, and financial stress. It is essential to create a supportive and understanding work environment that encourages open communication and addresses the specific challenges identified in the adversity quotient assessment. Additionally, fostering a culture of collaboration and providing resources for stress management can contribute to the overall well-being and effectiveness of teachers within the educational system.

Moreover, to improve the role-specific and generic competencies for leadership capability, school heads, the DepEd officials may prioritize school heads' professional development programs to enhance organizational and time management skills, provide training on effective change management strategies, and offer continuous learning opportunities for staying updated on educational trends and teacher engagement strategies. Implementing mentorship programs and peer learning networks can facilitate the sharing of good practices among school heads, while investing in technology training will empower school heads to utilize information technology effectively for communication and work functions. Strengthening these competencies will contribute to more effective school leadership and improved overall school performance.

In addition, as to the status and independence for work values of teachers, it is recommended that public elementary school teachers actively seek opportunities for professional development, leadership roles, and community engagement to enhance their sense of status and independence. Engaging in mentorship programs, networking with peers, and pursuing additional qualifications can contribute to career advancement and increased professional recognition. Teachers may proactively communicate their career aspirations and seek support from school administrators to align their roles with their values and aspirations.

Also, as to the self-determination/efficacy for school culture of teachers, it is recommended for school heads and teachers to collaboratively prioritize a culture of proactive problem-solving and preventative measures. Encouraging open communication, collaboration, and a shared sense of responsibility among teachers and staff can foster a more interdependent and supportive environment. Additionally, empowering school staff with greater autonomy in instructional decision-making and promoting a positive, enjoyable work atmosphere can contribute to a stronger sense of self-determination and efficacy within the school community.

Further, it was found that the best fitting model shows that the adversity quotient of teachers, leadership capability and work values of teachers have significant direct effect on the school culture of teachers. Hence, it is recommended that schools may prioritize targeted interventions to enhance the adversity quotient of teachers, leadership capability, and work values of teachers, recognizing their direct impact on shaping the overall school culture. Implementing professional development programs, fostering supportive leadership practices, and creating a positive work environment aligned with teachers' values can contribute to a more resilient, empowered, and collaborative school culture that positively impacts the teaching and learning experience.

For future researchers, it is recommended to delve deeper into the specific mechanisms through which adversity quotient, leadership capability, and work values collectively influence school culture. It is recommended to conduct mixed method research design like explanatory sequential approach with the qualitative analysis to further explain the quantitative results of the study. Additionally, exploring the moderating factors or contextual variables that might influence the strength of these relationships would contribute to a clearer understanding of the dynamics at play. Finally, investigating effective strategies for implementing and sustaining positive changes in adversity quotient, leadership practices, and work values within educational settings can offer practical guidance for

educators and policymakers.

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